

Signal Detection Theory and Drift-Diffusion Model are discarded from Yes-No and 2AFC contrast detection data of 1D and 2D CSF measures

Tzvetomir Tzvetanov

2023/06/22

The present document contains 3 proofs.

The first one is a snapshot of the directory where the main manuscript was written. One can see the dates for the different versions of the manuscript, from version 1 up to version 15 (see below).

The second document is the pdf of the presentation made during a laboratory seminar in USTC (February 2017), in the lab of Pr. Y.Zhou, presenting the main results about SDT not working to predict the differences between Yes-No and 2AFC tasks.

The third document is the draft number 15 of the manuscript which I decided to make public through this pre-print. I consider the main points about proofs that SDT and DDM models do not work are clear. Originally I wanted to go one step further and make a small “non-linear Signal Detection Model”. I am not in a proper psychological environment for making this last step.

I am convinced that the current manuscript is already sufficiently clear for other scientists to stop using and advertising these two models.

But my analysis may be wrong.

This is why I make it public.

I would like to emphasize that Dr. J. Huang made the measurements and collected the data in Pr. Y. Zhou's laboratory at USTC. The analysis was done entirely by me. I consider that all three of us have contributed to these results. All personal evolutions and behaviours of many individuals and groups since the data was collected and these major results were established (in 2017) do not matter what concerns to whom the discovery belongs.

Warning: If by some astonishing coincidence, I see a major scientific work that comes to the conclusions that the present analyses have given, with too similar of a design, I would deduce that these people are part of one or more secret networks that make scientific theft their main business.

Snapshot of the directory where the main manuscript was written that shows all versions with the associated date of modification.

Comparison of Yes-No *versus* standard 2AFC for contrast detection and CSF measurement

Tzvetomir Tzvetanov

School of Computer & Information, HFUT
& School of Life Science, USTC

2017/02/12

Presentation at Vis. Res. Lab., USTC

- Why comparing Yes-No & 2AFC for CSF measurement ?
→ Simulations of Yes-No & 2AFC in CSF designs:

- **BUT**

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- **BUT** Signal Detection Theory prediction of Yes-No vs. 2AFC psychometric functions:

- Problems/Issues:
 1. Lapse rate (in Yes-No & 2AFC) and Guess rate (in Yes-No) affect the psychometric function estimate.
 2. 2AFC takes longer time to measure, and for naive subjects they need more time to “learn” the task.

BUT

- Yes-No (that includes “no stimulus” trials for False alarm measure) can be used to measure the sensory threshold.

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Questions:

1. Are Yes-No and 2AFC measures of sensitivity at $d'=1$ the same ? (Once we adjust for lapse and guess rate)
2. How much faster is Yes-No ?
3. Which task subjects prefer ?
4. Any differences in “naive” and “experienced” subjects ?

- Experimental tests:

- 1) Two exp. Designs:

- 1D psych. function at one SF – better estimates of all parameters
- 2D CSF – for the function of interest in practical designs (lab, clinical, etc.)

- 2) Two tasks: Yes-No & 2AFC

- 3) For Yes-No – two global levels of perceived stimulus

- YN1: “low-k” – ~30-50% of trials perceived
- YN2: “high-k” – ~40-60% of trials perceived
- 2AFC: ~50% of trials correct responses (=perceived)

- 4) ~200 trials per psych. function estimate

- 5) Instructions:

- a) In Yes-No: report if saw or not the stimulus, and that 1 out of 4 trials there will be no stimulus.
- b) In 2AFC: which time interval the stimulus was present (there is always a stimulus in one of the two time intervals)

- 6) End of exp., which task was “better” (Yes-No vs 2AFC) and which YN was preferred (YN1 or YN2) ?

RESULTS for 1D psychometric function

– Data analysis:

→ fit 1D Weibull psych. function to each data set to extract:

(a) Lapse rate λ

(b) Guess rate γ

(c) Empirical contrast threshold c_{thr}

(d) Power β (slope)

$$\lambda + (1 - 2\lambda) \left[\gamma + (1 - \gamma) \underbrace{\left(1 - \exp \left(- (c/c_{thr})^\beta \right) \right)}_{\text{Weibull function}} \right]$$

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Examples of psychometric functions and fits

False alarm rate (n=50)

RESULTS: YN vs 2AFC

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$$\lambda + (1 - 2\lambda) \left[\gamma + (1 - \gamma) (1 - \exp(- (c/c_{thr})^\beta)) \right]$$

Yes-No & 2AFC measure the same empirical psychometric function !!

& independent of criterion/guess rate !!

If SDT correct
 → use of Yes-No is better because access to criterion k

RESULTS: YN1 vs YN2

$$\lambda + (1 - 2\lambda) \left[\gamma + (1 - \gamma) (1 - \exp(- (c/c_{thr})^\beta)) \right]$$

Summary Experiment 1: 1D psych.function

parameter	2AFC	YN1	YN2
lapse	0.0391	0.0123	0.0157
Guess rate	–	0.168	0.161
c_{thr}	0.0172	0.0168	0.0175
Beta (slope)	3.39	3.59	4.29
c_{sens}	0.0155	0.0127	0.0140
k	–	1.21	1.17
Median Time (min)	8.3	6.4	5.7

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CSF RESULTS (2D psychometric function)

– Data analysis:

→ fit 1D Weibull psych. function in contrast dimension

→ fit std CSF in SF dimension

(a) Lapse rate λ

(b) Guess rate γ

(c) Empirical contrast threshold c_{thr} at peak CSF

(d) Power β (slope)

(e) Peak SF

(f) Area logCSF

Examples of psychometric functions and fits

CSF RESULTS (2D psychometric function)

Summary Experiment 2: 2D psych.function

Parameter	2AFC	YN1	YN2
lapse	0.017	0.019	0.024
guess rate	–	0.19	0.19
peak CSF	79.7	86.8	88.8
beta	3.7	3.5	4.1
peak SF	1.27	1.44	1.34
C_{sens}	0.0114	0.0097	0.0099
AUlogCSF	2.20	2.31	2.32
Median Time (min)	7.9	6.2	5.4

Significance markers: * indicates p < 0.05, ** indicates p < 0.01.

Conclusion

- stop using std 2 intervals-2AFC and its analysis in any type of experimental design !!!
 - the measured psychometric function is the same as in a measure with single-interval Yes-No task BUT IN 2AFC YOU DO NOT KNOW SUBJECT'S CRITERION !!!
- for optimal Yes-No sampling, either:
 - use the non-parametric SIAM procedure of Kaernbach (1988) for taking into account subject's criterion
 - or
 - adapt FIG method to Yes-No design to also measure lower asymptote
- Yes-No measures are systematically much faster in measurement time, and the ones presenting “more perceived values” are also good, giving similar threshold estimates as “low-convergence point YN” methods.

Contrast detection data from Yes-No and Two-Alternative-Forced-Choice tasks discard classic SDT and drift-diffusion model: toward non-linear dynamics decision theory (nlDDT)

Tzvetomir Tzvetanov^{1,2}

¹ Anhui Province Key Laboratory of Affective Computing and Advanced Intelligent Machine, and School of Computer and Information, Hefei University of Technology, Hefei, P. R. China

² Hefei National Laboratory for Physical Sciences at Microscale, and CAS Key Laboratory for Brain Function and Disease, and School of Life Science, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, P. R. China

Abstract:

A small study was carried to compare contrast sensitivity measures between Yes-No (YN) and two-alternative forced-choice (2AFC) tasks. Its outcome is presented because it seems that the results show a much broader importance to the scientific community than originally sought by the author with the design of the study. That is, YN and 2AFC tasks demonstrated similar empirical functions instead of the widely accepted Signal Detection Theory (SDT) prediction. Two experiments were carried that compared the results of measuring visual contrast detection thresholds with YN and 2AFC tasks, in classical single spatial frequency 1D grating design (Exp.1) and in the spatial 2D Contrast Sensitivity Function (CSF) (Exp.2). Furthermore, attempt was made to manipulate observers' criterion in the YN task by performing two YN measures with different global stimulus visibility: with adaptive algorithms targeting low convergence points (low-YN) and with adaptive algorithms targeting high convergence points (high-YN). In Exp.1, the 1D psychometric function was measured and the parameters of contrast threshold, power (slope), lapse rate and guess rate (in Yes-No task) were extracted through a Weibull fit across the contrast dimension. Results showed that empirical contrast thresholds are similar across task designs, irrespective of the task and guess rate/false alarm rate of the subjects in the YN task. On the contrary slopes showed differences in the high-YN task from the 2AFC and low-YN tasks. Concurrently, when SDT is applied to YN and 2AFC results for extracting sensory thresholds of detection for each task the results demonstrated a strong correlation between the predicted 2AFC-to-YN thresholds difference and the putative criterion of the subject in the YN task. Comparing the results of low-YN and high-YN showed no threshold differences, no criterion difference and strong positive correlation between false alarms/criteria in both measures (i.e. observers tended to keep similar guess rates on different YN sessions), but demonstrated a higher slope of the detection curve for the high-YN measure. These results were also obtained in Experiment 2, which measured the 2D CSF, despite the stronger variability when measuring such a function. Possible design pitfalls of this current study are discussed, its results compared to literature reports, practical advises are proposed for threshold measurements, and theoretical consequences are drawn through the test of the "dynamic Signal Detection Theory", which seems to be much better supported by the behavioural data.

1 Introduction

Measuring perception of sensory features, as simple as detection of tones in hearing, or detection of luminance/contrast in vision, or more complex features as visual orientation, motion, texture etc., is a standard method in practical and research environments. Its foundation was laid down during 19th century (see Introduction of Luce (1986) and Link (1992)) and well formalised in the second half of 20th century in the generally accepted Signal Detection Theory (SDT), although different decision models are available (Luce, 1986; Link, 1992). One classic experimental method employed is the standard two-alternative forced choice (2AFC) task that is assumed, based on Signal Detection Theory (Green & Swets, 1966; Macmillan & Creelman, 2005), to discard the decision criterion of the observer and thus to lead to unbiased estimates of sensory thresholds. At the same time it is known that this method is prone to more variability in the estimates than simple Yes-No (YN) task. In the later observer's task is rather simple but SDT's internal criterion is a parameter that needs to be measured in order to deduce the threshold.

In this small study the two experiments that were carried assumed, based on SDT, that if one measures psychometric functions for visual detection of contrast with the two tasks of YN and 2AFC the respective psychometric functions should not be equal (Green & Swets, 1966; Nachmias, 1981). Instead the 2AFC should provide the correct unbiased estimate of the sensory threshold while the YN task should give an estimate that depends on observer's guess rate (false alarm rate). If the observer has a guess rate of 50% in the YN task then the YN task should provide a psychometric function slightly shifted toward lower stimulus intensities than the 2AFC one. With decreasing guess rates the YN psychometric function should cross and then be shifted toward stronger intensities from the 2AFC psychometric function.

This is visualised in Figure 1. Figure 1A depicts the standard SDT description in three dimensional representation with the axes of stimulus intensity and internal response as x - and y -axes and the z -axis representing their corresponding probabilities. A given stimulus intensity (no-stimulus with thin line; three stimulus levels with increasing intensity s_1, s_2, s_3 with thick black lines) creates an activation on the "Internal response" axis through the transducing function (here taken as a simple linear relation, thick red straight line). Assuming Gaussian distributions of the internal responses and applying a constant criterion k on each distribution provides the corresponding psychometric function for YN tasks (thick red sigmoid), written as:

$$P(S|s) = \int_k^{+\infty} p(y|s)dy = (1/\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma) \int_k^{+\infty} \exp(-(y - \mu_s)^2 / 2\sigma_s^2) dy \quad (1.1)$$

with μ_s being the mean effect of stimulus intensity s obtained through the transducer function mapping s to internal variable y ($p(y|s)$ is the probability density function to have y given s). The guess rate at stimulus of zero depends on the criterion and transducer. When k is expressed in noise centred and normalised form k^* (centred on the noise and normalized to its standard deviation) one obtains the guess rate from the relation:

$$\gamma = \Phi(-k^*) \quad (1.2)$$

with $\Phi()$ the cumulative normal distribution with unit variance.

To make the point more clear, in the practical example of contrast detection one can compute the psychometric functions for detection of a stimulus in the YN task for various criteria k^* and also in the criteria-independent 2AFC task (assuming difference model; see Methods for all computational details). This is depicted in Figure 1B for six YN functions k^* corresponding to six different criteria k^* (thin solid lines) and for the 2AFC psychometric function (thick black line). The vertical line at contrast ~ 0.014 corresponds to the sensory contrast c_s giving a d' -prime of one at which mean signal effect and mean of noise distribution are separated one standard deviation away from each other. From this graphic, one can see that to infer c_s from YN psychometric functions one has to measure the full functions including the guess rate. For cases with guess rates close to zero, the sensory

threshold is located in the lower portion of the curve and the functions shifted much strongly toward higher contrasts. This can be seen in Fig.1C where the psychometric functions from Fig.1B were corrected for the guess rate and plotted in the same probability range. It helps to visualise the systematic shift of the YN psychometric functions which is related to the guess rate.

The above description helps to understand the main idea and assumptions that are violated in the experiments reported below. The sections are organised as follows. Section 2 presents the experimental results of Experiment 1 and Experiment 2, then discusses about the results with respect to similar reports in the literature. Then, section 3 presents the tests of the drift-diffusion model on the data and the difficulties also encountered with the application of this decision model. Section 4 tests a non-linear dynamics decision theory to account for human detection-decision performance. The discussion summarizes the main findings and issues and the last section provides details of the Methods used throughout the work.

2 Testing classic SDT on YN and 2AFC data

2.1 Experiment 1: 1D psychometric function

In this experiment one dimensional psychometric functions of contrast detection were obtained in YN and 2AFC tasks for a total of 36 subjects and each measured with 200 trials (in YN tasks there were 50 blank trials). The theoretical psychometric function that was fit to the experimental data with Bayesian fitting was:

$$P(R = 1|c, \gamma, \lambda, c_{thr}, \beta) = \lambda + (1 - 2\lambda) \left(\gamma + (1 - \gamma) F(c, c_{thr}, \beta) \right) \quad (2.1)$$

It represents the probability to have response R of 1, in YN a “seen” response and in 2AFC a correct response, at contrast c and it includes lapse rate λ (e.g. May and Solomon (2013)) because it affects the other parameters estimates in the fitting procedure (Wichmann & Hill, 2001a,b). The two parameters c_{thr} and β define the empirical threshold and power (or slope) of the function, respectively. In the fitting procedure the Weibull function was used for $F()$ (see Methods) because it does not give practical differences from cumulative Gaussian functions (Quick, 1974) and it is also supposed independent of any underlying assumptions about the transducer model (but see May and Solomon (2015)).

In the experiments with YN task an attempt was done to manipulate the criterion of the observer. It was assumed that the criterion would be dependent on the global visibility of the stimulus across the block of measures. Therefore two YN blocks of measurement were carried. A first block sampled the psychometric function with two staircases whose mean convergence points were 25% and 75%

Figure 2: Example psychometric functions obtained in Experiment 1 for three subject. Top row for low-YN task and bottom row for the corresponding 2AFC task. Dots are experimental psychometric functions, obtained by binning contrast, and red sigmoids the resulting fit. In YN panels diamond symbols on the left represent the experimental false alarm rate obtained from 50 trials.

respectively, thus providing a theoretical mean “Yes” response rate of 50% for stimulus present condition; it is called low-YN. A second block sampled the curve with two staircases of mean convergence points of 33% and 85.7% that provide a theoretical mean “Yes” response rate of $\sim 59.5\%$ when stimulus present; it is called high-YN (always carried as last measure, see Methods).

Representative results for three subjects are presented in Figure 2. They allow to see the general effect of similarity of low-YN and 2AFC psychometric functions despite the differences in guess rates between subjects.

Sub-Figure 3(a), graphics A-D, compares the distributions of the psychometric function parameters obtained in the low-YN and 2AFC tasks. Lapse rates between both tasks (Fig.3(a)A) seemed to be independent. There were globally higher lapse rates in 2AFC tasks than in low-YN tasks (Table 1). Concerning the guess rate and false alarm rate in the low-YN task (Fig.3(a)B), they had mean values of about 17% indicating that a large pool of observers tended to be rather conservative in responding “Yes” when stimulus intensity was so low that it was not seen. Across observers there was also a clear and strong relation between both, that is, the false alarm rate globally, across observers, represents the guess rate while individual discrepancies up to 10% can be found (see the data points deviating from the diagonal and Table 1). These effects are due to the general methodology of including the false alarm rate into the fitting procedure. The empirical thresholds of the observers (c_{thr} in equation (2.1)) are plotted in Figure 3(a)C. Despite the rather large distribution of contrast thresholds present across observers all values lay around the diagonal line of equality and did not exhibit any systematic difference between the two tasks (Table 1). Last, the power (β) of the psychometric function, which relates to the slope at threshold, is presented in Fig.3(a)D. It is found that this parameter is not different between the two tasks (Table 1).

From these first results it appears that empirical psychometric functions for YN and 2AFC tasks, once adjusted for their respective guess rates and lapse rates, are equal (Fig.3(a)C-D). To demonstrate it in a complementary way the putative SDT sensory threshold c_s was extracted from both measures (Figure 3(a)E), which in the case of YN task is guess rate dependent. It is apparent that 2AFC sensory thresholds estimates are globally higher than their YN counterparts (Table 1). When their difference is plotted against the normalised criterion k^* (obtained from Equation (1.2); cases of $\gamma < 0.01$ were set equal to 0.5/50, Macmillan and Creelman (2005)) a strong positive correlation is observed ($r=0.69$, $p=0.00011$; Fig.3(a)F). These two results indicate that, based on SDT, adjusting for guess rate in the YN task led to a lower sensory threshold estimate.

These global effects were also observed when comparing the 2AFC task to the second high-YN measure (Figure 3(b)). The parameters mean values with their standard deviations for each task are

Figure 3: Comparison of parameters of psychometric functions in low-YN, high-YN and 2AFC tasks for the 36 observers. In each sub-figure are compared the obtained parameters of psychometric functions in the corresponding two tasks for the 36 observers (panels A-D), prediction of contrast sensitivity threshold c_s in both tasks (panels E), and relation of threshold difference 2AFC-to-YN to observers' criteria in YN (sub-figures (a) and (b), panels F). In (c) graphic (F) plots the criteria of both YN tasks. Red crosses depict means with 95% confidence interval, and in sub-figure 3(c)B light- and dark-red crosses are means of FA and Guess rates.

presented in Table 1. As can be seen the lapse rates were again higher in the 2AFC task, empirical thresholds c_{thr} were not different, and sensory thresholds c_s were different (high-YN task provided lower thresholds, as the low-YN task). Guess rates and False alarm rates in the high-YN task were globally indistinguishable across observers (Fig.3(b)B), despite that individual observers could have strong differences of up to $\sim 25\%$. The only systematic change is that the high-YN task exhibited a statistically significant increase in power (β) of the psychometric function that indicates steeper functions (mean power increase of 0.9). Again, there was also a strong correlation between the difference in predicted sensory threshold c_s of 2AFC and high-YN tasks and the high-YN criterion ($r=0.43$, $p=0.0077$; Fig.3(b)F), exactly as for the 2AFC versus low-YN task comparison.

Parameter	2AFC	low-YN	high-YN	2AFC vs low-YN	2AFC vs high-YN	low-YN vs high-YN
λ	3.9% \pm 5.1%	1.2% \pm 1.8%	1.6% \pm 2.7%	$z=3.25$ ** $p=0.0011$	$z=3.21$ ** $p=0.0014$	$z=1.71$ $p=0.087$
γ	N/A	17% \pm 16%	16% \pm 13%	N/A	N/A	$t(35)=0.446$ $p=0.66$
c_{thr}	-1.76 \pm 0.29	-1.77 \pm 0.31	-1.76 \pm 0.30	$t(35)=0.730$ $p=0.47$	$t(35)=-0.418$ $p=0.68$	$t(35)=-1.01$ $p=0.32$
β	3.4 \pm 1.1	3.6 \pm 1.0	4.3 \pm 1.3	$t(35)=-0.853$ $p=0.40$	$t(35)=-3.41$ ** $p=0.0016$	$t(35)=-2.74$ * $p=0.0096$
c_s	-1.81 \pm 0.29	-1.90 \pm 0.30	-1.85 \pm 0.29	$t(35)=4.30$ ** $p=0.0001$	$t(35)=2.65$ ** $p=0.0012$	$t(35)=2.03$ $p=0.050$
k^*	N/A	1.21 \pm 0.78	1.17 \pm 0.64	N/A	N/A	$t(35)=0.569$ $p=0.57$

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of parameters of Experiment 1 for each task and their statistical comparison (see Methods for details). Contrast thresholds are expressed in log-10 values. Lapse and Guess rates are expressed in percentages. Because for each parameter three comparisons are performed 0.05 significance level is Bonferoni corrected to 0.0167 (indicated with (*)) in front of the p-value) and 0.01 to 0.0033 (indicated with (**)) in front of the p-value)(see Methods for statistical procedures).

Figure 4: Example of CSF data (filled dots and crosses) and fit results for the two YN tasks and the 2AFC task. See individual legend for details. Thick red curves are the best fit CSF and thin curves are iso-probability lines between 0 and 1 in steps of 10% that help visualise the fitted power/slope (or equivalently the spread). FA stands for False Alarm and fitted guess and lapse rates are provided in each panel.

Last, comparing the low-YN and high-YN tasks (Sub-Figure 3(c)) showed only a statistically significant increase of psychometric function power (β) with higher convergence point, while the empirical and sensory thresholds were not different (see also Table 1). Remarque: sensory thresholds comparisons are just significant at $p=0.05$ (for single test) but do not survive statistical correction for multiple comparisons, while the power values are significantly different (mean increase from low-YN to high-YN of 0.7). Additionally, despite that the measures were done in two separate blocks with breaks up to tens of minutes in-between, the results showed a strong tendency of observers to keep a similar criterion level across the two YN tasks (Table 1 last row; correlation $r=0.76$, $p=0.000024$; Figure 3(c)B,F).

From these results it appears that 2AFC and YN tasks provide similar empirical threshold estimates, while the power/slope of the function increased in YN tasks as global visibility of the stimulus increased (or mean convergence point of the adaptive procedure increased). This point will be analysed further in the discussion. One major result is the equality of empirical thresholds irrespective of the observer's guess rate in the YN task, which makes as consequence that if one applies SDT to extract the sensory threshold c_s , there are systematically lower prediction of c_s in YN task than in 2AFC task. Concurrently, the c_s difference between 2AFC and YN task was systematically correlated to the guess rate (criterion) of the observers.

2.2 Experiment 2: 2D psychometric function

The second experiment measured the spatial contrast sensitivity function (CSF) of the subjects that represents the contrast sensitivity of the observer at various spatial frequencies (SFs) (Jindra & Zemon, 1989; Wilson & Wilkinson, 2003; Watson & Ahumada, 2005; Wang, Wang, Huang, Zhou & Tzvetanov, 2017). It is a 2D function and its exact shape across the SF dimension depends on experimental conditions as for example stimulus parameters and light environment. Various bell-shaped mathematical forms provide a satisfactory description of the measurement (Watson & Ahumada, 2005). The important point here is that on a SF vs. sensitivity (inverse of contrast threshold) plot it exhibits a peak between SFs of 0 to 4 cycles per degree (c/d), representing observers' best visual sensitivity, and that along the contrast dimension the 1D contrast psychometric function is obtained from SDT. Thus, when one measures this 2D function, the 2AFC and YN tasks have the same SDT predictions about the empirical and sensory thresholds along the contrast dimension as the 1D function in the previous Experiment 1 (see also Introduction). Therefore all theoretical relations between threshold measures are valid.

An example of CSF measures is presented in Figure 4 that depicts the results of one observer for the low-YN, high-YN and 2AFC tasks. This observer guess rates in the two YN measures are around 25%. The obtained CSF in the three measures are very similar. Because empirical thresholds vary across SFs, to compare the results across tasks for all observers three major parameters of the CSF

Figure 5: Parameters of CSF function obtained in Experiment 2 for the three tasks of low-YN, high-YN and 2AFC. Each sub-figure compares parameters for the corresponding two tasks. Red crosses are means with 95% confidence interval. In sub-figure (c), graphic B, the light-red and dark-red crosses are means of guess and FA rates respectively.

are extracted: the peak SF, the empirical contrast threshold at peak SF, and the area under the log-10 CSF (AUlog10CSF). The example provides the typical CSF obtained in normal measures of subjects for short time presentations of stimuli: peak SF between 0 and ~ 4 c/d (at low SFs the CSF may exhibit asymptotic behaviour with peak at 0 Hz), mean maximum contrast sensitivity in the range 80-110 (mean contrast thresholds between 0.009-0.013), and AUlog10CSF in the range 2-3.

First, the results of 2AFC and low-YN tasks are compared in sub-figure 5(a). Lapse rates of observers were globally low and indistinguishable between the two measures (Fig.5(a)A; see Table 2 for means and statistical comparisons). Across observers the guess and false alarm rate of low-YN task showed a broad range of values, from 0 up to 55%, and the mean was $\sim 19\%$ showing that the observers were globally conservative in responding “Yes” when stimulus contrast was so low that stimulus was not seen. While across observers the two rates were not different few persons exhibited differences of up to 10% (Fig.5(a)B). The peak SF of both measures were not different (Fig.5(a)C), neither the empirical contrast thresholds c_{thr} at peak (Fig.5(a)D). Additionally, the 2AFC and low-YN values of these two parameters laid around the diagonal of equality and exhibited strong correlations across observers (peak SF: $r=0.49$, $p=0.003$; c_{thr} at peak: $r=0.74$, $p<0.001$). The power of the function along the contrast dimension of both measures were not different (Fig.5(a)E). Last, the AUlog10CSF also showed good reproducibility between the two tasks of low-YN and 2AFC across subjects (Fig.5(a)F; correlation: $r=0.83$, $p<0.001$).

From these first CSF results it appears that empirical psychometric functions in 2D obtained in 2AFC and YN tasks are equal and independent of the FA/guess rate of the subject, exactly as in the 1D measures of psychometric functions in Experiment 1. Applying SDT theory for extracting the putative sensory thresholds c_s in 2AFC and low-YN task gave strong systematic differences between both predictions (Fig.5(a)G). Furthermore, the differences in sensory thresholds were strongly correlated to the YN criterion of the observers (Fig.5(a)H; $r=0.65$, $p<0.001$).

Parameter	2AFC	low-YN	high-YN	2AFC vs low-YN	2AFC vs high-YN	low-YN vs high-YN
λ	1.7±2.6%	2.0±3.5%	2.5±3.4%	z=-0.41 p=0.68	z=-0.18 p=0.86	z=-0.19 p=0.84
γ	N/A	19.4±18.7%	14.2±17.0%	N/A	N/A	t(34)=0.34 p=0.74
c_{thr} at peak	-1.90±0.16	-1.94±0.15	-1.95±0.13	t(34)=1.95 p=0.059	t(34)=2.32 p=0.026	t(34)=0.63 p=0.53
peak SF	0.10±0.24	0.16±0.27	0.13±0.24	t(34)=-1.25 p=0.22	t(34)=-0.63 p=0.53	t(34)=1.00 p=0.32
β	3.7±1.3	3.5±1.4	4.2±1.2	t(34)=0.49 p=0.62	t(34)=-1.48 p=0.15	t(34)=-2.58 * p=0.014
c_s	-1.94±0.15	-2.01±0.18	-2.01±0.12	t(34)=2.62 * p=0.013	t(34)=2.88 ** p=0.0068	t(34)=0.31 p=0.76
k^*	N/A	1.03±0.65	1.09±0.70	N/A	N/A	t(34)=-0.64 p=0.52
AUlog10CSF	2.20±0.43	2.31±0.48	2.32±0.36	t(34)=-2.26 p=0.030	t(34)=-2.87 * p=0.0070	t(34)=-0.32 p=0.75

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of parameter results of Experiment 2 for each task and their statistical comparison (see Methods for details). Contrast thresholds, peak SF and sensory threshold are expressed in log-10 values. Lapse and Guess rates are expressed in percentages. Same format as Table 1.

The above results were also present when comparing the 2AFC task with the high-YN task (Fig.5(b) and Table 2) and comparing low-YN to high-YN task results (Fig.5(c)). In this later case, low- and high-YN tasks comparison showed that subjects globally kept a similar false alarm rate (Fig.5(c)B), or equivalently a similar criterion (Fig.5(c)H). Nevertheless there were two differences. The first difference is that the data of the high-YN task provided a psychometric function power (β) higher than the low-YN task, while all other parameters showed similar values and strong correlations between both measures. The second difference was in the AUlog10CSF that showed statistically significant difference between 2AFC and high-YN task and a trend of difference for 2AFC vs. low-YN task (see Fig.5(b) and Table 2, bottom row). After visual inspection of the individual fits this last effect seemed to come from the high SF portion of the CSF curve that tended to be higher in the YN measures. This effect is noted but not discussed further.

2.3 Intermediary conclusion

The two experiments reported above showed that empirical psychometric functions measured with the two classic tasks of Yes-No and 2AFC are similar. That is, once the measures are adjusted for lapse and guess rates the theoretical function of the subject that underlies perception and response to the stimulus have similar empirical thresholds. Complementary to this, when applying SDT to infer the sensory threshold of perception, theoretically independent of the task, the resulting values were systematically different between the two tasks and the difference 2AFC to YN was strongly correlated to the YN guess rate/criterion of the subjects. Furthermore, manipulating stimulus visibility through the adaptive algorithm, by targeting a higher convergence point, showed an increase in psychometric function slope. Noteworthy, these results were obtained in two separate experiments that measured 1D and 2D psychometric functions. Consequently, the two experiments provide strong evidence against SDT applicability in the classic contrast detection measures.

2.4 Change in power for high-YN: genuine or artefact?

One side question that arises is the issue of the increase in power for the high-YN task. This effect was present in both Experiments (Table 1 & 2, row β) though weaker in Experiment 2. Before concluding that adaptive staircases targeting globally higher convergence points, thus providing more visibility of the stimulus, do measure different underlying psychometric functions it is

necessary to check whether the experimental design, which introduced a sampling asymmetry, could have led to the observed differences.

Because in the high-YN task the psychometric function was sampled in a different way from the low-YN and 2AFC tasks by putting more measures in the “high” range of the psychometric function, it could be that this procedure tends to overestimate the slope parameter. For that reason Monte-Carlo simulations were performed of a theoretical observer with mean experimental parameters ($\lambda=0$, $\gamma=0.17$, $c_{thr}=1.7$, $\beta=3.4$) and Exp.1 exact adaptive sampling and fitting methods were carried. Results are depicted in Table 3. They showed a global equality in psychometric function estimates between the three types of task/sampling plans. While there was a slight systematic increase of power estimate in comparison to the theoretical value (~10%) and very small differences between YN and 2AFC tasks, importantly the high-YN sampling provided very similar power estimates to the low-YN and 2AFC. From these simulations, it is concluded that the experimental methodology coupled with the psychometric function analysis method is not a factor influencing the observed differences between powers.

Task type	λ (0)	γ (0.17)	C_{thr} (0.0174)	β (3.4)
low-YN	0.008±0.010	0.16±0.04	0.0171±0.0011	3.6±1.0
high-YN	0.005±0.007	0.16±0.05	0.0171±0.0012	3.6±0.9
2AFC	0.009±0.012	N/A	0.0170±0.0011	3.8±1.0

Table 3: Mean with standard deviations of Monte-Carlo simulations of theoretical experimental measure of a mean psychometric function (parameter values in top row). Simulations of 1000 measurements were performed for each task condition. See text for details.

From another point of view, since the method for measuring psychometric function varies the intensity of the signal within one block of measurement one may expect that standard SDT's prediction in this situation may lead to higher slopes with higher convergence points (for a related development and discussion see section 7.4 in Sperling and Doshier (1986)). Because of this experimental manipulation the subject may use a higher decision criterion with higher convergence points and thus change the slope of the psychometric function (see Introduction and Figure 1B,C). This explanation seems unlikely because high-YN tasks systematically led to higher powers while no effect was observed on the guess rates/criteria in both experiments presented here. This was further confirmed by a non significant correlation between change in guess rate and change in power from low- to high-YN (in Exp.1: $p=0.32$; in Exp.2: $p=0.77$).

Therefore, the observed changes in slopes of YN task must be taken as a genuine effect of experimental manipulation, either some practice effects due to the first two blocks of measure (high-YN was always measured last), or either stimulus sampling strategy that displays some specific characteristics of the human detection-decision system that is unrelated (or possibly weakly related) to observer's guess rate.

2.5 Previous comparisons of YN and 2AFC tasks and SDT failure

A major result is that YN and 2AFC tasks provide similar empirical thresholds. This was unexpected because the initial assumption was that SDT will predict YN and 2AFC differences. This assumption was based on the classic SDT (Green & Swets, 1966; Macmillan & Creelman, 2005) as well as reports in the visual domain of YN tasks leading to higher empirical thresholds than 2AFC tasks (Nachmias, 1981). Looking more broadly into the literature, i.e. going away from the vision literature, it seems discrepant results as the one reported in this study were already present.

First, by investigating and using the “sweet point” maximum-likelihood automated method developed by Green (1993) for measuring psychometric functions in YN tasks, Gu and Green (1994) and Leek, Dubno, He and Ahlstrom (2000) reported that empirical auditory detection

thresholds measures were very consistent between 2AFC and YN tasks for normal-hearing subjects as well as for hearing-impaired persons. Noteworthy, as in the current results, this equality was present across numerous observers with a broad range of thresholds, but also in different types of threshold measures: absolute thresholds, thresholds obtained in masking experiments, thresholds of experienced and inexperienced psychophysical observers. Sadly, their studies either only targetted YN advantage in task design and time for data collection (Leek et al., 2000), or stated that "due to the poor estimation on the false alarm of the maximum-likelihood yes-no procedure" it was not possible to compare 2AFC vs. YN threshold differences (Gu & Green, 1994). Thus, neither study went further in discussing why 2AFC vs. YN gave similar empirical thresholds, neither did they analyse the guess rate relation to the difference of YN to 2AFC thresholds despite their intriguing outcomes.

Second, in yet another field of psychology, recognition memory, researchers have also reported discrepancies (Kroll, Yonelinas, Dobbins & Frederick, 2002; Langley, 2006). Specifically, when computing the d' value of 2AFC and YN tasks it is systematically found that when subjects are more conservative the YN tasks seem "better" in comparison to the classic 2AFC estimates, i.e. observers showed better discriminability performance in YN task. Specifically, Kroll et al. (2002)'s Experiment 1 did show that the d' difference 2AFC to YN was systematically positively correlated to the observers' YN guess rate/criterion, exactly as in the results found in the present study. They further proposed that two plausible SDT modifications provided a reasonable account of the observations, though applied on a different data set than the one showing the discrepancies. The first one is particular to the recognition memory literature with a "recollection model" that is not discussed here. The second one is the unequal-variance model of SDT (Green & Swets, 1966), i.e. signal and noise internal distributions have different variances. This modification cannot account for the results found in the current study, as well as in the studies measuring directly the psychometric function (Gu & Green, 1994; Leek et al., 2000), for it can not account the independence from guess rate/criterion of observers' similarity of YN and 2AFC empirical thresholds.

3 Testing the drift-diffusion model (DDM) on the YN and 2AFC data

The above short description of previous reports of SDT failure combined with the current experimental results leads to an important question: what detection theory can accommodate unchanged empirical thresholds in 2AFC and YN tasks once adjusted for guess rate and lapses? Does it also provide an explanation of the increase in power/slope of the psychometric function with sampling plans targeting higher convergence points?

Multiple different theories of signal detection were proposed and tested already (for an early summary see Gaussin (1972); Luce and Green (1974)). These theories, though some had very different theoretical assumptions about the internal representation of the stimulus and the decision process, were able to explain for some, sometimes different, parts of the data. One type of models, generally called sequential sampling models, saw an important surge in the recent three decades because they seem to provide a better link to neurophysiological systems of decision processes (Smith, 2000; Gold & Shadlen, 2001; Gold & Shadlen, 2002; Gold & Shadlen, 2007; Ratcliff & McKoon, 2008; Ding & Gold, 2013; Gold & Ding, 2013; Forstmann, Ratcliff & Wagenmakers, 2016). These models also incorporate response latency to the stimulus (for a deep-dive in the early data and theories see Luce (1986) and Link (1992)). Their major advantage is that they account simultaneously for both measures of probability detect and response latency (Smith, 2000; Miller, 2015).

In this section are tested the predictions of the drift-diffusion model (DDM) (Forstmann et al., 2016; Ratcliff, Smith, Brown & McKoon, 2016) in a way closely related to the work of Palmer, Huk and Shadlen (2005). This model with two-response alternatives allows to predict the two behavioural parameters of the subject, the proportion responses to each response-alternative and the response times to each alternative. Concerning the question of interest in the current data – similar empirical

Figure 6: Illustration of DDM model and its predictions. (A): example of DDM outcome for 6 trials with response outcomes R_A (red curves) and R_B (blue curves); it shows that the decision time, the time point for first crossing one of the response boundaries, contains strong randomness because of the stochastic nature of the accumulating process; red and blue bell-shaped curves are the corresponding RT distributions for each outcome (parameters: $A=1$, $B=0.4$, $\mu=0$, $\sigma=1$). (B,C): example of expected mean psychometric functions for both the proportion of responses R_A and the response times for both R_A and R_B as a function of stimulus contrast (see text for details; $A=1$, $B=0.4$, $\sigma=1$, $T_{resid}=0.35$ seconds). (D) Theoretical relation at zero drift between response times T_B , T_A , and proportion responses P_A ($T_{resid}=300$ ms); height of surface along T_A is colour coded to help visualisation; 2D contour lines across each dimension are also drawn (solid black lines on each surface) to help visualise the 3D surface (for an animated rotation of the surface together with data points see Supplementary Figure 1).

proportion correct curves in YN and 2AFC tasks – it is analysed how this model fares with respect to predicting the psychometric relations between the three measures of low-YN, high-YN and 2AFC.

3.1 Theoretical background of DDM

In the DDM the dynamics of the decision variable U is governed by the simple diffusion equation with drift rate, here written in stochastic differential equation form (Smith, 2000; Miller, 2015):

$$dU = \mu dt + \eta(t) \quad (3.1)$$

where μ is a constant drift rate, related to the strength of the input, and $\eta(t)$ is a Brownian motion of a white Gaussian noise with variance σ^2 . The decision is made when the variable U reaches one of two predefined boundaries, here denoted A and $-B$, that correspond to the two predefined responses R_A and R_B (see Figure 6A for illustration of model and decision variable time evolution). The first boundary that is reached is the given response and the decision time is the corresponding time. This simple stochastic process has been well analysed and psychometric function predictions of proportion responses P_A and P_B and the corresponding expectations on decision times $T_A \equiv E[T_{D,A}]$ and $T_B \equiv E[T_{D,B}]$ have been derived as (Luce, 1986; Palmer et al., 2005) :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} P_{A,\mu \neq 0} = \left(e^{2\mu B/\sigma^2} - 1 \right) / \left(e^{2\mu B/\sigma^2} - e^{-2\mu A/\sigma^2} \right) \\ P_B = 1 - P_A \\ E[T_{D,A}]_{\mu \neq 0} = \left((A+B)/\mu \right) \coth \left((A+B)\mu/\sigma^2 \right) - (B/\mu) \coth \left(B\mu/\sigma^2 \right) \\ E[T_{D,B}]_{\mu \neq 0} = \left((A+B)/\mu \right) \coth \left((A+B)\mu/\sigma^2 \right) - (A/\mu) \coth \left(A\mu/\sigma^2 \right) \\ \lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} P_A = B/(A+B) \\ \lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} E[T_{D,A}] = (A^2 + 2AB)/3\sigma^2 \\ \lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} E[T_{D,B}] = (B^2 + 2AB)/3\sigma^2 \end{array} \right. \quad (3.2)$$

Remarque: the experimental response times contain multiple components of processing and thus they are commonly modelled as the sum of the above DDM decision times plus a residual time of

processing T_{resid} (sometimes called non-decision time); the above equations for T 's are obtained from the density distribution of response times that can be computed exactly (Ratcliff, 1978; Luce, 1986; Palmer et al., 2005; Voss & Voss, 2008) and these densities have been used to infer decision processes; they are illustrated in Figure 6A (red and blue bell-shaped curves) and can be used for inferring the DDM parameters when using a fixed stimulus strength; for the present purpose these distributions are irrelevant and the mean T_D 's are sufficient for psychometric analyses and model inference, as described in Palmer et al. (2005).

From the above equations, it is possible to completely define the psychometric functions as a function of contrast if one defines the relation between drift μ and input strength, here contrast c . If we take the same equation as for Figure 1 (equation (6.5), with $\mu=r(c)$ and fixing $r_0=0$; e.g. Smith, Ratcliff and Wolfgang (2004); Palmer et al. (2005)) the model is fully defined and predicts proportion and mean response times as a function of contrast (Figure 6B,C).

From this short presentation of the DDM and its previous application on psychometric functions fitting (Palmer et al., 2005), it appears that this model could be applied on the data of the current two experiments. Nevertheless, inspection of model's predictions (Fig.6B,C) and individual raw data showed that the recorded RTs did not span a sufficiently large range of stimulus intensities necessary for constraining the model parameters, and that some peculiar data behaviour were difficult to explain with the above model assumption. In particular data showing RTs' strong decrease when P_A has practically saturated are scarce, when not present at all. As a consequence, in a first analysis, a different strategy is taken, similar to the SDT case, by inferring relations between measured variables, which turned out to show unexpectedly interesting outcomes when applied on single task predictions.

3.2 Testing the DDM on individual tasks

First it is noted that when the DDM is applied on a given task it makes strong and rigid predictions about the experimentally measured psychometric variables. This can be seen in Figure 6B,C and equations (3.2). In particular the case of zero drift ($\mu=0$) is interesting. For example, P_A at contrast zero (Fig.6B) is the guess rate of the subject between the two alternatives, and it depends on the two boundaries. In a similar way, the RTs T_A and T_B at contrast zero (Fig.6C) also depend non-linearly on these two boundaries. By using equation (3.2) at $\mu=0$, it is possible to compute the relation between these three measured variables and eliminate any model parameters, for example T_A as a function of the two others, P_A and T_B , which gives:

$$T_A = T_B(1 - P_A^2)/P_A(2 - P_A) \quad (3.3)$$

Noteworthy, in order to compare the data to the model there is only one free parameter, the residual time of processing T_{resid} that is model independent and simply shifts the above surface along the RTs axes. This prediction provides a very strong constrain on the relation between the three experimental parameters. This surface is plotted on Fig.6D. It allows the reader to see that the non-linearity of this three-way relation makes the corresponding two-way relations variable (see contour plots on each surface of the 3D box). That is, if one considers only two parameters, the prediction strongly depends on the third discarded parameter and thus contains important model variability.

Therefore, it was first checked whether within a given task the data follows the above DDM relation by extracting the relevant variables from the ad-hoc psychophysic fits obtained in the previous section. For that reason, all the data were reprocessed to include also the RTs of the subjects. The data of YN tasks are simple to process by taking model "Response A" as subject's "Yes" answers. In the 2AFC tasks "Response A" is taken as "Interval I" answers. In this later task the data of proportion correct responses were refit by splitting the functions of proportion correct into two functions, one for each interval and allowing for simple guess rate differences between the two intervals (see Methods; and for a related approach and discussion on this topic see Garcia-Perez and Alcalá-Quintana (2011a,b)). Concerning RTs, Fig.6B,C show that RTs do not vary strongly up to about 25% increase of P_A . Consequently, to compute the RTs at zero drift for each response type,

Figure 7: Results for Experiment 1 of testing DDM predictions on psychometric measures relations of individual task at zero drift. (A) Three dimensional view of the theoretical relation (mesh surface) and the data points of each task (see legend; $T_{resid}=0.4$ s). (B,C,D) Two-way scatter plots between the three variables. (E) Mean distance Data to DDM prediction as a function of residual processing time. Shaded regions are 95% confidence intervals of the means. (F) Distance of individual data points to closest DDM prediction at $T_{resid}=0.6$ seconds. Legend for all panels in (A).

any trial with contrast below 25% of the underlying psychometric function was selected ($F()$ in equation (2.1)).

Figure 7 presents the results for Experiment 1. First, the 3D representation of the three parameters P_A (guess rate) with experimental response times T_A and T_B showed clear data regularity in the three measures. The two YN tasks had data with a large majority of the RTs clearly below the DDM predictions, but the guess rates (P_A) spanned only half of the range (0 to 0.5). The 2AFC results for RTs data were approximately equally distributed around the surface and their P_A 's (guess rates) were distributed between 0.2 and 0.9. Noteworthy, these results exhibited a systematic difference between data and DDM prediction, that is, P_A smaller than ~ 0.6 had RTs lower than the prediction (below the surface) and vice versa for P_A greater than 0.6. These observations are dependent on the residual time of processing, but it is found that adjusting DDM's prediction with different T_{resid} is unsuccessful at matching the model to the data. This can be visualized also in the simpler 2D scatter plots of the three variables (Fig.7B,C,D; see Table 4 for correlations). Because the relation between the two RTs is nearly linear for all three tasks (Fig.7B, Table 4), increasing T_{resid} shifts the DDM surface approximately in parallel to the YN tasks data while more 2AFC data move below the surface.

	Task type	T_A vs T_B	P_A vs T_A	P_A vs T_B
Experiment 1	low-YN	0.87 (p<0.001)**	0.06 (p=0.50)	0.32 (p=0.02)*
	high-YN	0.78 (p<0.001)**	0.17 (p=0.31)	0.48 (p=0.01)*
	2AFC	0.81 (p<0.001)**	-0.04 (p=0.44)	0.05 (p=0.99)
Experiment 2	low-YN	0.58 (p<0.001)**	-0.49 (p=0.007)**	0.06 (p=0.88)
	high-YN	0.71 (p<0.001)**	-0.33 (p=0.13)	0.08 (p=0.72)
	2AFC	0.89 (p<0.001)**	0.13 (p=0.26)	0.18 (p=0.15)

Table 4: Correlations of the variables P_A , T_A , T_B in Experiment 1 and Experiment 2 computed near drift of zero. Significant correlations are indicated with (**) at $\alpha=0.01$ and (*) at $\alpha=0.05$.

Figure 8: Results for Experiment 2 of testing DDM predictions on psychometric measures relations of individual task at zero drift. Same format as Figure 7, but in (E,F) distance is closest for $T_{resid}=0.640$ seconds in high-YN task.

To transform these observations into quantitative values the signed smallest distance between each datum and the DDM prediction was computed for different T_{resid} values (see Methods). Negative values show data points below the surface along the T_A axis. Figure 7E shows the results for the three tasks for a range of values of T_{resid} . The two YN tasks show systematic differences from zero that are significant at 5% despite that around $T_{resid}=0.6$ s the mean distance is the closest to zero. While the 2AFC task mean shows a slight decrease with increasing T_{resid} , its mean is not different from zero. Nevertheless, further inspection of the 2AFC data at $T_{resid}=0.600$ (Fig.7F) shows that the individual points distances have significant increase with higher P_A (correlation: $r=0.45$, $p=0.007$), as observed from the 3D plot (Fig.7A). Such an effect was not present for the two YN tasks (low-YN: $r=0.07$, $p=0.70$; high-YN: $r=0.07$, $p=0.66$). From this reanalysis of the data of Exp.1, it appears that the DDM predictions are difficult to reconcile with the individual tasks of YN and 2AFC, with response times and guess rate not following the expected DDM relation.

The data of Experiment 2 were also processed the same way as above. The results are presented in Figure 8. Both YN tasks showed data points below the DDM prediction while the 2AFC data P_A 's spread between ~ 0.2 - 0.8 (Fig.8A-D) and also exhibited the surface crossing around $P_A \sim 0.6$. The two RTs correlation (Fig.8B) was again strong while the two other correlations were not strong or showed different outcomes from Experiment 1 (compare Fig.7C,D and Fig.8C,D, and Table 4). Importantly, the mean signed distance data-to-DDM gave similar outcomes as a function of residual time T_{resid} (Fig.8E), with the two YN tasks always significantly below the surface and the 2AFC task mean moving below the surface with longer residual time. The closest distance of the high-YN task is found at ~ 0.640 seconds. The 2AFC data exhibited strong positive correlation between P_A and individual data-to-DDM distances (Fig.8F; $r=0.46$, $p=0.024$), while the two YN tasks did not show such an effect (low-YN: $r=-0.06$, $p=0.84$; high-YN: $r=-0.34$, $p=0.15$). In summary, Experiment 2 demonstrated very similar results as Experiment 1 and the same difficulty to reconcile the data with the DDM predictions.

3.3 Intermediary discussion

From the above comparisons of each individual task to the DDM prediction for the particular and interesting case of “zero drift”, it appears that the global data do not follow this model. On the other hand, the model is used in its simplest form with the least parameters and assumptions. Few important points need to be discussed.

First, in the analysis response times were taken as mean values for each response alternative and thus both T_A and T_B contain the residual time of processing. Instead, one can rewrite equation (3.3) by taking the RTs differences $\Delta T \equiv T_A - T_B$ and their means $T_M \equiv (T_A + T_B)/2$, thus leaving T_{resid} only in one variable. This approach, although interesting per se, gives equivalent results to the current presentation because it simply transforms linearly the variables in another 3D space. The results are similar and the visualization provides similar insights as above despite that the 3D surface of the DDM prediction is more folded than the current presentation (results not shown).

Second, some peculiarities of the 3D results in Figures 7 and 8 need to be pointed. The residual time of processing necessary for making the closest match of data-to-DDM across observers is around 0.600-0.640 seconds (Fig.7E, Fig.8E). This value is high given that in general literature reports of T_{resid} are between 0.250 and 0.500 seconds (Palmer et al., 2005; Ratcliff & McKoon, 2008). The origin of these differences might be the instructions and experimental design, because they did not provide any information to the subjects about response time delays and emphasized accuracy for measuring contrast thresholds. Nevertheless, the mean RTs across observers were in Exp.1: low-YN – 0.790 s, high-YN – 0.678 s, 2AFC – 0.799 s; in Exp.2: low-YN – 0.771, high-YN – 0.686, and 2AFC – 0.809 seconds. When one considers that the psychometric relation for response times was mainly measured in its higher asymptote region (Fig.6C), it seems that these mean values are comparable to what would be expected in such experiments (Palmer et al., 2005) where reported decision times are much lower than 0.6 seconds. Further below it is shown that these high T_{resid} combined with globally normal RTs hinted toward an incorrect model assumptions.

Third and very notable, all data points $\{P_A, T_A, T_B\}$ of the three tasks appear to be approximately laying onto a single surface (almost a plane) in the 3D space that is close to the plane $T_A = T_B$, but not on it, which is very apparent on the 2D correlation plots (panels A-D in Figs.7-8). In fact, this relation at zero contrast seems systematic across tasks and repeated measures, and obtained in both experiments. This indicates that the relation between these three variables might be much simpler, or at least that the way the DDM incorporates that case needs serious reconsideration for modelling the behavioural results.

3.4 Effects of other parameters on data-to-DDM comparison

The above results seem a very strong case against the DDM. The particular condition that was analysed, zero drift rate, makes the model predictions very simple. It turns out that this DDM prediction (equation (3.3)) is insensitive to the value of the diffusion constant (noise level), because this variable is eliminated when computing equation (3.3), or equivalently can be integrated as a general scaling factor.

On the other hand variability around starting point or boundary heights has been argued as important components for explaining changes in RTs distributions (Ratcliff & McKoon, 2008; Ratcliff et al., 2016). Such changes have non-linear effects onto RTs distributions, but also the means. These variabilities have stronger effects on the shortest of the two RTs, corresponding to the closest boundary, by decreasing the mean RTs. Since in the current data for the YN tasks P_A 's were below 0.5 the fastest theoretical RTs are the T_B 's. Therefore, the above variabilities should decrease more the theoretical mean T_B 's than T_A 's and thus the mean difference between data and DDM should not improve (see the 3D plots in Fig.7A,8A).

One important issue is the assumption of zero drift rate at contrast zero. Until now all the analysis relies on this assumption. At first, the author assumed naturally that when no stimulus is present the DDM's drift rate must be zero, as also assumed in Smith et al. (2004); Palmer et al. (2005). But from the perspective of the DDM the exact zero setting of the drift rate is undefined, and thus when no stimulus is presented it could be biased toward one or the other alternatives. Consequently, at zero contrast the proportion responses P_A and P_B , as well as their corresponding RTs, could also be dependent on a non-zero drift rate. This possibility combined with the boundary heights makes the overall predictions more complex.

Figure 9: Scatter plots of DDM parameters $\{A, B, \mu\}$ vs. experimental variables $\{P_A, T_A, T_B\}$ at contrast zero, or their most pertinent combinations thereof, showing the strong and systematic correlations found across all measures of Exp.1 and Exp.2.

It is important to note that in its original meaning the drift rate is directly related to stimulus strength, or evidence, and it is assumed unbiased (Link, 1975; Link & Heath, 1975; Ratcliff, 1978; Smith et al., 2004; Palmer et al., 2005). Instead of this, assuming non-zero drift in no-stimulus conditions makes the drift rate a combination of “stimulus strength evidence” and “bias” (observer or internal or biased stimulus representation or biased response; to be decided someday). While the current author is not fond of such an interpretation, especially because it is believed that theoretical models should provide independent parameters for different theoretical concepts (see criterion and sensitivity in SDT), it is a possibility that stimulus evidence, which is integrated over time, is a biased quantity and thus in experiments mixing different stimulus strengths the conditions with the smallest stimulus strengths have non-zero drift rates. (to make things even more complicated, it is also plausible to have different diffusion constants for each alternative, i.e. random steps toward boundaries A and B have different values, thus making the DDM even more complex; but this possibility is not pursued here). This could be interpreted as a “biased input evidence” that could be some top-down modulation of the pure “feed-forward” stimulus related input, or biasing the decision by setting a “natural” drift toward one response alternative instead of the second. Overall, this possibility is biasing the response alternatives through an additional and different mechanism than the boundary heights.

The extension of the DDM with biased drift rate was easy to test on the data at contrast zero. Because there are three measured variables and three parameters, the inferred DDM parameters are unique, i.e. as in a linear regression with two data points, and always predict the data. The important point is that to predict the data at contrast zero the drift rate must be varied. Analysing the results across the two Experiments and the three blocks of measures (low-YN, high-YN, 2AFC), it is found that the few systematic relations of how the DDM explains the data across the six measures are very simple: (1) RTs are affected by boundary heights and (2) response bias at zero contrast (i.e. guess rate) is affected by drift rate (for a more detailed result overview of data-to-DDM correlations, see Appendix). These effects are depicted in Figure 9 presenting the three main and interesting correlations. The major systematic results are that drift rate allows to set the response bias between the two alternatives (Fig.9A,D), while boundary height difference adjusts the difference in RTs (Fig.9B,E) and total height adjusts the mean RTs (Fig.9C,F).

3.5 Comparing predictions for the three measures of each experiment

Until now it was not tested how the model predicts differences between types of task, which was the original question for testing the DDM because of SDT's inconsistencies in predicting the YN and 2AFC tasks outcomes.

The *digression* in the above three subsections showed the difficulty to match the classic DDM to individual data of each task for the conditions when no stimulus is present unless the drift rate contains also a bias term. This was very apparent in the YN tasks but it turned out that the 2AFC data also needed such an adjustment. Now the question how the DDM relates the psychometric variables obtained in the three measures (low-YN, high-YN, 2AFC) can be investigated in more details.

The two Experiments were carried for comparing the classic psychometric functions of proportion detect between different tasks and sampling methods. The predictions of the DDM depend on the three parameters $\{A, B, \mu\}$ (equation (3.2), and assuming diffusion normalised variables, see Fig.6B,C). As it was noted, the DDM parameters totally define the psychometric relations for proportion correct and RTs. For model completeness, the parameter of drift rate is taken as a linear combination of bias μ_0 and contrast dependent effect ($\mu = \mu_0 + \mu(c)$) corresponding to stimulus coding. Since this later value is assumed independent of the task design and decision process its prediction from the different measures should give similar values. Thus, the chosen strategy is to compute the DDM prediction of the contrast related drift threshold $\mu_{thr} = \mu(c_{thr})$ on the proportion correct curve given the DDM parameters obtained from contrast of zero. By using the three parameters $\{A, B, \mu_0\}$ obtained in the previous subsection (e.g. Fig.9) it is possible to infer the value of drift threshold by solving numerically:

$$(1 - p_{thr})e^{2B(\mu_0 + \mu_{thr})} + p_{thr}e^{-2A(\mu_0 + \mu_{thr})} - 1 = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

where:

$$p_{thr} \equiv P(c_{thr}) = 1 - (1 - \gamma)e^{-1} \quad (3.5)$$

is obtained from the ad-hoc model (equ. (2.1), taking out lapse rate). Furthermore, this contrast related drift is classically directly associated to the neuronal contrast response function, which at low contrasts is nearly linear or a simple power function of contrast (Smith et al., 2004; Palmer et al., 2005). Consequently, the differences between predicted $\log_{10}(\mu_{thr})$ in the different measures are not affected by the exact values of power and amplitude.

	2AFC	low-YN	high-YN	2AFC vs. low-YN	2AFC vs. high-YN	low-YN vs. high-YN
Exp. 1	0.11±0.18	0.40±0.31	0.45±0.25	t(35)=-5.91 **p<0.001	t(35)=-8.87 **p<0.001	t(35)=-2.15 p=0.038
Exp. 2	0.10±0.18	0.33±0.18	0.39±0.19	t(36)=-7.17 **p<0.001	t(36)=-8.79 **p<0.001	t(36)=-3.52 **p=0.001

Table 5: Results of predicted drift thresholds (mean±st.dev. of \log_{10} values) and their comparisons across tasks and measures. Significant values are Bonferroni corrected from 0.05 to 0.016 (**) and 0.01 to 0.0033 (*).

The results of predicted μ_{thr} of all three tasks are presented in Table 5. It is apparent that almost all three tasks in both experiments show strong differences (out of low-YN vs. high-YN for Exp.1). Thus, it is concluded that DDM cannot account for similarities of proportion correct curves outcomes between different measurement techniques and observers' tasks, as observed in the analyses of the two experiments in section 2.

3.6 General discussion of DDM tests and summary

All the above analyses of DDM application on the current data showed two very different approaches that gave interesting outcomes. First, it is found that the DDM applied on single task condition for predicting the psychometric functions of proportion correct and response times, and relevant relations between measured variables, has difficulties unless one releases an important original model assumption of unbiased relation between drift rate and stimulus strength. Second, assuming bias, it is found that the DDM predicts very different thresholds between the three different measures of the same contrast detection experiment, while no differences were present in the ad-hoc analyses. Each of these approaches is discussed separately below.

DDM application on single data set

The first intriguing finding is the necessity to release the important assumption about unbiased drift rate. It is classically considered as directly representing the evidence of the stimulus, or equivalently taken as stimulus strength related. In modelling psychometric relations as proportion correct and response time versus stimulus strength previous works have directly used known simple neuronal response functions as replacement of drift rate (e.g. for contrast responses Smith et al. (2004); Palmer et al. (2005)). The check of whether the data at zero contrast follow the expected relation of DDM variables for zero drift rate failed. Thus, this common assumption is false.

A second intriguing fact is the consistency of the data $\{P_A, T_A, T_B\}$ at zero contrast and obtained across the two experiments (Figs.7,8). The 3D data points of all measures and observers lay approximately on a surface that can be described with only two parameters of the DDM, the third one being a linear combination of the two others. To illustrate this point, the author rapidly found “by hand” (trial and error) a satisfactory relation for each Experimental data, with the constrain that the mean signed distance across observers of each measure is not different from zero and that there are no spurious correlations for any of the three measures, as found in Figs.7,8F (the relations are, for Exp.1: $B=A-0.05+0.1\mu$; for Exp.2: $B=A+0.1+0.3\mu$; same method as for Figs.7,8). Figure 10 depicts the residuals signed distance of the individual points for each experiment. This simple example shows that the relations of the three measured variables $\{P_A, T_A, T_B\}$ at zero contrast seem to be one parameter simpler than the DDM predictions while the mathematical form is consistent (equ. (3.2)). Because it is found that the drift at zero contrast must be non-zero, the DDM’s explanation of the no-stimulus condition is unsatisfactory, with one parameter too much, and no explanation why the data should be constrained in such a way.

Another difficulty of the DDM predictions, not mentioned until now, relates to the high-contrast asymptote of the response times. It is important to note that the model predicts vanishing decision times with higher contrasts (or strengths) of the stimulus, that is, when drift rate tends to very high values (infinity) RTs converge to the residual RTs. This can be visualised in the example of Fig.6C, where the RTs for both alternatives converge toward the residual time of processing. Nevertheless, it is well known that choice response times, as in the DDM and experiments analysed here, contain a minimum decision component about stimulus identity that is of about 0.050-0.200 seconds longer than equivalent simple RTs (Luce, 1986; Pins & Bonnet, 1996). Furthermore, this decision component is present also when variation of RTs due to stimulus strength is taken into account (Pins & Bonnet, 1996; Bonnet & Link, 1998; Link & Bonnet, 1998). As a consequence, all applications of the DDM need to take into account the “high-contrast” asymptote such that it integrates the minimum decision time. In its simplistic form, when no information about it can be extracted from the experimental design, it can be assumed a constant toward which the decision times converge at high stimulus strengths. While it gives a simple solution to the evanescence of decision times in the classical DDM, it opens a new question about the high limit of the drift rate. In order to have a non-zero low bound on decision times it is necessary to have an upper bound on drift rate (see equ. (3.2)): for example, $A=1$ and $\min(T_A)=0.05$ gives $\max(\mu)=20$ (almost independent from the value of B). Thus, the saturation of μ with stimulus strength is also a necessary component of the DDM. This makes the drift rate having a natural relation to firing rate, since this last variable is bounded

Figure 10: Residual distances of individual data to the adhoc surface modelled with only two DDM parameters, with means \pm s.e.m. for each measure presented on the rightmost side of each plot. All correlations of distance vs. P_A are not significantly different from zero.

between minimum and maximum firing rate of the neurons. But on the other hand, this adds a supplementary complication for DDM parameters estimation, with a biased and bounded drift rate, plus an interaction between asymptotic decision time with residual processing time, and with further complex effects as for example differences between asymptotic T_A and T_B 's (left to the reader to visualise).

DDM comparison between measures and tasks

In the current study the asymptotic decision time was not available because responses were collected in the transition region of proportion correct (detection region) far from the asymptote of RTs. This issue does not affect the estimates of drift threshold μ_{thr} because the curve for P_A essentially saturates in the early expansion region of the contrast related drift rate $\mu(c)$. Thus, the predicted differences between measures and tasks are valid and any saturation of amplitude effect, which is assumed the same across all conditions, would only scale the distributions and not change the statistics.

The comparison of the three measures was done by extrapolating the drift threshold of each measure. An equivalent method would have been to fit each individual data with a parametric form of the DDM assuming all parameters free $\{A, B, \mu_0, k, p\}$ (amplitude k and power p describe the relation contrast-to-drift: $\mu(c) = kc^p$) and then comparing the predicted values between measures, especially for amplitude and exponent. It is expected that it would have given the same result.

Previous reports of biased drift rate

In a deeper literature overview about the DDM, it became apparent that the finding of necessarily biased drift rate was already noted by previous researchers as well as its consequence on model's parameters interpretation.

First, Ratcliff and collaborators have already noted that such "biasedness" seems necessary for adjusting the DDM to the data (Ratcliff, 1985; Ratcliff, 1987; Ratcliff, Thapar & McKoon, 2003; Gomez, Ratcliff & Perea, 2007), with the consequence that drift rate and boundaries have intertwined relations in setting the common criterion and sensitivity measures of SDT.

Second, this negative side was also noted by Angela Yu and collaborators (Yu, 2013), and stated in a clear way in Shenoy and Yu (2012):

While augmenting DDM with extra parameters gives it additional power in explaining subtleties in data, this also diminishes the normative interpretability of DDM fits by

eliminating its formal relationship to the optimal SPRT procedure. As a consequence, when the behavioral objectives change [...] DDM cannot predict a priori what parameters ought to change and how much.

In line of the above clear statements about the DDM parameters, experimental reports have demonstrated that the drift-rate is not only based on sensory information. Instead it was found to contain also other informations as for example speed of response, value, or reward (Churchland, Kiani & Shadlen, 2008; Hauser & Salinas, 2015; Salinas, 2015).

Despite this conceptual difficulty about parameters interpretation, it is noteworthy that the model applied to the 2AFC and YN measures of contrast detection of the current data gave different underlying sensory thresholds for each measure. Thus, in its current form it cannot be used for predicting the sensory sensitivity of the subjects.

Summary

In summary, the DDM is unable to explain the results of the two Experiments that collected psychometric functions of contrast detection with three different measures and in two different designs. This was found for individual task results of response probabilities and response times but also for comparisons across tasks of predicted sensory thresholds.

4 Empirical relations between parameters of proportion correct functions, $P(c)$, and response times

The above analysis of the DDM showed that proportion responses ($P_{A,B}$) and response times ($T_{A,B}$) provide important constraints about model validity. The question therefore arises whether RTs show any relation to the empirical findings obtained in section 2 about global equality of contrast thresholds but differences in other parameters. In this section, the experimental data is further analysed by considering the relations between P 's and T 's, and possible empirical explanations of the observed results in section 2 based on previous knowledge, as for example the speed-accuracy trade-off (Macmillan & Creelman, 2005).

5 Non-linear dynamic decision theory (NL2DT)

One major point in the approach of the drift-diffusion model, but it seems also for all sequential sampling models, is that it considers the time to arrive at the decision as a stochastic process that is obtained from integrating noisy information. Thus, the distributions of response times are due to the random (noise) components in the variables that are involved in the decision process.

In opposition to this, a different approach considers the decision process as arising from purely non-linear dynamic interactions between populations of neurons where noise is not the major contributor, if not absent at all.

- comparing YN and 2AFC: make the plots δ_{μ_thr} vs. δ_{c_thr}
- literature on comparing the DDM in different tasks ?

6 Methods

The two experiments shared the same design and setup and differed only in the number of spatial frequencies presented to the subject and a different method to present the staircase adaptive procedures at a given SF, as described below.

6.1 Subjects

A total of 37 observers participated in the study, including the author. They were recruited from the institute or the laboratory, and all but the author were naive to the purpose of the experiments. They provided written consent for their participation, the experiments followed the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki and were approved by the Ethics committee of the School of Life Science at USTC. About half of the subjects were classified as experienced observers based on their previous numerous participation in experiments in the laboratory at the School of Life Science of USTC, and the remaining persons were classified as inexperienced. Three observers were ran by the author and the remaining persons by Ms. Dr. J.-F. Huang, whom the author thanks for acting as a technical assistant in this study, at the Vision Research Laboratory of the School of Life Science (USTC). All data were collected in the second half of December 2016 while the author was still working at USTC.

6.2 Experimental methods

The setup consisted of an Intel based PC running Windows 7 and stimuli programmed under Matlab (Mathworks Inc.) with the help of the psychophysics toolbox 3 (Brainard, 1997; Pelli, 1997). Stimuli were presented on a Sony Multiscan G520 21 inches monitor working at 85 Hz and 1600 x 1200 pixels resolution. Subject sat in a dimly illuminated room on a chair with their head stabilized with a chin-rest at 4 meters from the screen. They responded on a keyboard on predefined keys. The luminance of the monitor was calibrated at least 30 minutes after each powering of the monitor, and the background luminance of the screen was fixed at 20 cd/m².

Stimuli were vertically oriented cosine gratings seen through a circular window of diameter 2 degrees. The phase was random from trial-to-trial. The border was smoothed to the background with a cumulative Gaussian of 0.015 deg. standard deviation. The grating spatial frequency was 4 c/deg. in Experiment 1 and for Experiment 2 eleven spatial frequencies were chosen from 2^{-0.5} up to 2^{4.5} cycles per degrees in half octave steps. Grating contrast was varied to measure the psychometric functions of detection, as described in the procedure further below.

There were two possible tasks for the observer. The first task was a classic Yes-No design, where the observer had to respond whether they saw a stimulus in a single presentation. The second task was a classic two-interval forced choice design, where the target stimulus randomly appeared only in one of two possible intervals and the observer had to report which interval, first or second, contained the target.

The experimental procedure was as follow. For the YN task, the observer had to keep fixation at a small dot centred on the monitor and started each trial by a keyboard press. Then, 150 ms after its offset the stimulus, or a blank screen with background luminance, was presented for 150 ms accompanied by a high auditory tone. The observers had to respond whether they saw or not a stimulus, and they were instructed that randomly across the measurements in ¼ of the trials there will be no stimulus on the monitor. For the 2AFC task, the observer had to keep fixation at a small dot centred on the monitor and started each trial by a keyboard press. Then, 150 ms after its offset two intervals of 150 ms, each accompanied by a high auditory tone, were presented, separated by 500 ms time delay. One interval contained the target stimulus while the other interval had the background luminance. Observers had to report in which time interval, first or second, they saw the stimulus, and they were instructed that there is always a stimulus in one of the two intervals. In all conditions there was no feedback given to the persons as to the correctness of their responses.

To measure the psychometric function along the contrast dimension, the contrast of the stimulus at a given spatial frequency was varied based on the up-down staircase procedure (Kaernbach, 1991). For Experiment 1, which measured the psychometric function of contrast detection along a single spatial frequency, for the low-YN task two convergence points of 75% and 25% were defined, with steps up-down of 3/1 and 1/3 respectively in steps of 0.1 log-contrast units; 75 trials were assigned to each staircase and additional 50 trials were assigned to the blank condition, giving a total of 200 trials for the observer. The second high-YN design used convergence points of ~85.7% and 33%, with steps up-down of 6/1 and 1/2 respectively. In the 2AFC task, two staircases of 100 trials each and steps up-down of 3/1 were defined and they varied based on trial's correct/wrong response. Additionally, stimulus presentation was equally distributed between the two intervals of presentation, with half of the trials in the first interval and half in the second, independently of the staircases and subject's responses. For Experiment 2, at each of the eleven spatial frequencies (SF), one staircase was used to sample the contrast dimension as follows. In the YN tasks, SFs $\{2^{0.5}, 2^{1.5}, 2^{2.5}, 2^{3.5}, 2^{4.5}\}$ were assigned convergence points 75% (low-YN) or 85.7% (high-YN) and the remaining SFs convergence points 25% (low-YN) or 33% (high-YN), with 13 trials per staircase and additional 55 blank trials for false alarm estimate. In the 2AFC task all staircases had convergence points 75% and 18 trials were assigned to each. This design provided a total of 198 trials for CSF estimate in both types of task. Furthermore, in all conditions for the first 3 trials the steps of the staircases in log-contrast unit were 3 times bigger, thus allowing a faster convergence to the transition region. Start contrasts were ~0.0133 in Experiment 1 and $\{0.013, 0.012, 0.011, 0.010, 0.01, 0.011, 0.012, 0.017, 0.027, 0.059, 0.186\}$ at the respective eleven SFs of Experiment 2. In a block of measurement, all conditions were randomly presented on a trial basis.

The two experiments were carried in two separate sessions of about 30 minutes each. In one session the observer performed the 1D measurements (Experiment 1) and in the other session the 2D CSF measurement (Experiment 2). In one session, three blocks were measured: one block of the 2AFC design, one block of the low-YN task, and one block of the high-YN task. This third block was always ran last. The two other blocks were randomly presented across observers as first and second measures. Each observer ran training for 40 trials of each task for getting accustomed to the stimuli and response mapping. After a block was finished, the instruction screen for the next block was presented on the screen until the person pressed a predefined key to start the new block of measures, and they were allowed up to about 10 minutes of break between block measures. YN and 2AFC tasks used different keyboard keys for avoiding key confusion across tasks: the 'Y' and 'U' keys in YN, and left/right arrows for 2AFC.

Additionally to the key responses and response times of the observers to each stimulus presentation, supplementary parameters were recorded as: (1) duration of measurement for a given task; (2) preference of the observer for YN versus 2AFC task; (3) preference of the observer for block of low-YN in comparison to block of high-YN. Response times are defined with respect to the start time of stimulus onset; in 2AFC task with respect to the start of the second interval of presentation.

6.3 Data analysis

Data analysis was carried by fitting predefined psychometric functions to each data set. The basic psychometric function, which gives the probability to have response R of 1 ("Yes" response in YN task and correct response in 2AFC task) at a given contrast c , for contrast detection at a given spatial frequency, was defined as (Equation (2.1) reprinted):

$$P(c) \equiv P(R = 1 | c, \gamma, \lambda, c_{thr}, \beta) = \lambda + (1 - 2\lambda) \left(\gamma + (1 - \gamma) F(c, c_{thr}, \beta) \right)$$

with γ the guess rate of the observer and λ the lapse rate. Function $F()$ was taken as the Weibull function written as:

$$F(c, c_{thr}, \beta) = 1 - \exp \left(- (c/c_{thr})^\beta \right) \quad (6.1)$$

that defines the empirical threshold c_{thr} as the contrast to arrive at ~ 0.63 value of $F()$, and β is related to the steepness/slope of the function.

For the 2D spatial CSF measure, the contrast threshold c_{thr} varies as a function of SF in an inverse bell-shaped form, here taken as the three parameters function (Wilson & Wilkinson, 2003):

$$c_{thr}(f|a, b, M) = (ab)^a \exp(-a) / \left(M f^a \exp(-f/b) \right) \quad (6.2)$$

with f the SF of the stimulus, $1/M$ the minimum contrast threshold across SFs, and (a, b) relate to the slopes of the rising and decaying parts of the sensitivity curve.

The function (Equation (2.1)) was adjusted to a given data set of contrasts and responses $\{c_i, R_i, i=1..n_{tr}\}$ by using Bayesian fitting (Treutwein & Strasburger, 1999) and maximizing the posterior:

$$p(\theta|\{c_i, R_i, i = 1..n_{tr}\}) = p(\theta) \times p(\{R_i, i = 1..n_{tr}\}|\theta, \{c_i, i = 1..n_{tr}\}) \quad (6.3)$$

where $p(\theta)$ is the prior of the vector of parameters ($\theta = \{\lambda, \gamma, c_{thr}, \beta\}$ in 1D and $\theta = \{\lambda, \gamma, M, a, b, \beta\}$ in 2D) and the second term is the likelihood defined as:

$$p(\{R_i, i = 1..n_{tr}\}|\theta, \{c_i, i = 1..n_{tr}\}) = \prod_{i=1}^{n_{tr}} \left(P(c_i) \right)^{R_i} \left(1 - P(c_i) \right)^{1-R_i} \quad (6.4)$$

where $P(c_i)$ is defined in Equation (2.1) and the negative of the log-posterior was used for the function to minimize by means of the simplex algorithm. The priors were set as flat for all but the lapse λ and β parameters in a range of realistic values: the lapse prior was set as a Beta probability density function (pdf) with parameters $a_\lambda=1.1$ and $b_\lambda=10.9$ such that the mode of the pdf is at 0.01; the β prior was set as a Gamma pdf with parameters $a_\beta=3$ and $b_\beta=2$ such that the mode of the pdf is at 3. The other parameters had allowed ranges as: (i) γ in YN task within $[0,1]$ and in 2AFC task fixed at $1/2$; (ii) c_{thr} in Exp.1 within $[0,1]$; (iii) in 2D CSF measures a within $[0,10]$, b within $[0,20]$, and M within $[1,1000]$.

The data collection was carried under Matlab (Mathworks Inc.) but model fitting, data analyses and plotting was done under GNU Octave (Eaton & others, 2017) with custom written scripts and functions.

6.4 Statistical analyses

Statistical tests were performed as follows. Lapse rates were compared using the Wilcoxon non-parametric test with assumed normal distribution. Contrast thresholds were log-10 transformed and then compared with paired t-test. Guess rate, criterion and power values (β) were compared with paired t-tests. Correlation analysis used Spearman's method.

6.5 Computational details for Figure 1

Figure 1B presents YN and 2AFC psychometric functions for contrast detection. They were obtained by assuming a theoretical neuron responding to stimulus contrast c following the hyperbolic ratio function:

$$r(c) = r_0 + a(1 - c_{1/2}^n) c^n / \left(c^n (1 - 2c_{1/2}^n) + c_{1/2}^n \right) \quad (6.5)$$

The parameters are: r_0 – background firing rate; a – maximum amplitude of firing for $c=1$; n – power defining the shape; $c_{1/2}$ – half-amplitude constant corresponding to the contrast to arrive at firing of half-amplitude $r_0+a/2$. This mathematical form is obtained from the more classic hyperbolic ratio equation (Albrecht & Hamilton, 1982):

$$r(c) = r_0 + r_{max} c^n / (c^n + c_{50}^n) \quad (6.6)$$

by a change of variable such that:

$$\begin{aligned} r(c = 1) &= r_0 + a \\ r(c = c_{1/2}) &= r_0 + a/2 \end{aligned} \quad (6.7)$$

Variance of neural response was taken as background firing rate r_0 corresponding to a Fano factor of one and then decision criterion k (here firing rate; e.g. Tolhurst, Movshon and Dean (1983); Britten, Shadlen, Newsome and Movshon (1992)) was computed as:

$$k = r_0 + \sqrt{r_0} k^*. \quad (6.8)$$

Psychometric functions for YN were obtained by applying Equation (1.1) with transducer Equation (6.5) and for 2AFC the difference model. Numerical values were: $r_0=5$, $a=100$, $n=3$, $c_{1/2}=0.05$.

6.6 Computation of sensory threshold c_s

In the YN task the sensory threshold that corresponds to a d-prime of one, i.e. signal's value that creates internal response at one standard deviation from the noise distribution, is computed as follows. Given the noise centred and normalized criterion k^* (Equation (1.2)) one has the relation:

$$P(c_s) = \Phi(1 - k^*) = \Phi(1 - \Phi^{-1}(\gamma)), \quad (6.9)$$

which used in the Weibull approximation of the psychometric function (Equations (2.1) and (6.1)) gives:

$$c_s = c_{thr} \left(-\ln \left(\frac{1 - \Phi(1 - \Phi^{-1}(\gamma))}{1 - \gamma} \right) \right)^{1/\beta}. \quad (6.10)$$

6.7 Main parameters derivation from CSF fits

Equation (6.2) provides the empirical contrast threshold as a function of stimulus SF. In the main text three major parameters, not directly present in Equation (6.2), are analysed: peak SF, empirical threshold at peak (still noted c_{thr}), and AUlog10CSF; they were computed from the three CSF parameters $\{M, a, b\}$ as follows: peak SF corresponds to the product of parameters a and b , resulting values below $2^{-0.5}$ were artificially clamped at $2^{-0.5}$ because it is the minimum SF measured in the experimental design; c_{thr} at peak is the inverse of M ; the area under the log-10 CSF was obtained from analytic integration of the CSF equation in the log-space between the minimum and maximum SFs used in the experiment ($2^{-0.5}$ and $2^{4.5}$). The analytic integration gave the following equation:

$$\text{AUlog10CSF} = \frac{1}{(\ln(10))^2} \left[Y \ln(M) + \frac{1}{2} a Y^2 - \frac{1}{b} \exp(Y) \right]_{Y_{\min}}^{Y_{\max}} \quad (6.11)$$

with Y taken as the natural logarithm of SF f .

6.8 Methods for tests of the DDM

For the purpose of DDM model tests, first the data of the 2AFC tasks were refit by splitting the psychometric function into two functions for each interval. Stimulus presentation was equally distributed across intervals, each interval contained 100 trials (Exp.1) or 99 trials (Exp.2) with various levels of contrasts and their responses. Equation (2.1) was used for the fitting by defining γ as the guess rate of the first interval, which is interpreted as subject's proportion of responding "Interval 1" when stimulus contrast was so weak that it was not seen. By symmetry $(1-\gamma)$ is the guess rate of the second interval, while both intervals assumed the same parameters of lapse (λ), threshold (c_{thr}), and slope (β). Although further model development could be done, e.g. testing more complex interval response structures or differences in functions of proportion correct between the two intervals (Garcia-Perez & Alcalá-Quintana, 2011a,b), the current experimental design was originally not intended for such a detailed analysis and thus it was found difficult to make more

complex model fits to the data. This is especially true because of the relatively low sampling at the lowest asymptote of the 2AFC psychometric function, which barely allows for extension to guess rate parameter fitting. It is important to note that while the lowest asymptote sampling is low the shift in guess rate between the two intervals changes the overall function of proportion correct for both intervals (Garcia-Perez & Alcalá-Quintana, 2011b). This effect allowed this simple extension of the fitting procedure to two intervals.

Response times selection was carried as follows. First, RTs were analysed globally and scrutinized for particularities. For Experiment 1, in the YN tasks the distributions of RTs exhibited classic bell-shaped histograms with tails toward longer RTs (Ratcliff, 1993). Visual inspection allowed to observe that (1) in cases where subjects had low false alarm rate the number of RTs at zero or very low contrasts was relatively low for “Yes” answers, (2) the RTs means across subjects varied in a large range (e.g. in Exp.1, low-YN task had min: 0.507 s, max: 1.190 s, and across subjects mean±SD: 0.790±0.199 s), (3) few subjects exhibited large lapse rates that was also apparent in too many short RTs (below 0.200 s) even at high contrasts of the stimulus; (4) some subjects’ RTs evolution with stronger stimulus contrasts seemed to follow the expected decrease while for other subjects it was hard to notice such a behaviour. Thus, for selection of RTs near “zero drift” it was decided to use RTs within 0.100 s and 3 s and for contrasts measures below the 25% of $F()$ (the Weibull approximation, equation (6.1)). This allowed to have a large majority of mean estimates of T_A and T_B with at least ten RTs values (low-YN had 28 subjects, high-YN had 29 subjects, and 2AFC had 32 subjects with at least 10 RTs). For the 2AFC task, RTs selection followed the same procedure as above.

For Experiment 2, RTs selection followed the same procedure as above, with one specificity related to the 2D CSF shape. Because the contrast sensitivity function is measured across spatial frequencies (SFs), RTs were also spread across different SFs. Since RTs near-zero contrast should be independent from the SF of the stimulus, any trial with contrast lower than the 25% of $F()$ along the contrast dimension was selected as “zero drift” condition. This also allowed to have a large majority of mean estimates with at least ten RTs values (low-YN: 34 subjects; high-YN: 32 subjects; 2AFC: 36 subjects).

The signed distance i^{th} data to DDM prediction was computed in a simple 3D cartesian way:

$$d^i = \text{sign}(T_A^i - T_A^M) \times \min \left(\sqrt{(P_A^i - P_A^M)^2 + (T_A^i - T_A^M)^2 + (B_B^i - T_B^M)^2} \right) \quad (6.12)$$

with superscript “M” indicating DDM value. The closest absolute distance was found by discretizing the 2D space $\{P_A, T_B\}$ in 0.01 probability and 0.010 seconds steps and computing the T_A ’s, then the minimum distance was selected.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Relation of experimental parameter at contrast zero between the three measures

Figure 11 presents scatter plots of the experimental data obtained at contrast zero plotted to compare the values between measures of low-YN, high-YN, and 2AFC of a given Experiment.

It shows few global effects:

- RTs are strongly correlated between tasks, i.e. observers tend to keep similar global timing strategy in their response selection (panels D,G,E,H,F,I) that seems independent of the task and measure;
- differences in RTs between the two response-alternatives are correlated between YN measures but not between YN and 2AFC measures (panels J-L);
- RTs in high-YN are globally faster in comparison to low-YN and 2AFC (panels D,G,F,I);
- guess rates are correlated between YN measures but not between 2AFC and YN measures (panels A-C);

8.2 Correlation results between DDM parameters and measured variables

Table 6 presents correlations between the DDM parameters, including some of their combinations considered to be mainly influencing one of the experimental measures, and experimental measures. The three combinations of parameters were used because they are thought to influence independently the difference in RTs, the absolute RTs, and the relative guess rate between the two alternatives. Because the amount of correlations that are carried are rather extensive and the major

Figure 11: Within experiment correlations of the individual parameters at contrast zero $\{\gamma, T_A, T_B, \Delta T = T_A - T_B\}$ for the three tasks (low-YN, high-YN, 2AFC). Legend in panel (A). Correlation values are given in each panel for the corresponding Experiment 1 (r_1) and 2 (r_2) (only correlations in panels B,C,K,L are not significant, after Bonferroni correction for $n=3$ comparisons).

interest of the study is to compare model predictions between the three measures, correlations are marked that are only present systematically across all measures.

Across the two experiments and all three blocks of measures (Tasks), it is found that drift rate is the main contributor to guess rate adjustment, while the boundary heights affect the corresponding RTs and their differences. Some specific, systematic and interesting effects are present within YN tasks, especially the correlations of P_A vs $B/(A+B)$ and other boundary parameters, but they are not of importance in the current work.

	Task	Parameter	vs. P_A	vs. T_A	vs. T_B	vs. ΔT	vs. T_M
Experiment 1	low-YN	A	** -0.41	**0.57	*0.30	**0.65	**0.46
		B	-0.06	**0.48	**0.59	0.03	**0.53
		μ	**0.68	**0.49	**0.56	0.04	**0.54
		$A-B$	** -0.55	*0.39	-0.07	**0.92	0.19
		$A+B$	-0.29	**0.57	**0.43	*0.43	**0.52
		$B/(A+B)$	**0.32	-0.04	0.28	**-0.58	0.11
	high-YN	A	*-0.32	**0.74	0.29	**0.83	**0.58
		B	0.29	*0.34	**0.75	*-0.36	**0.55
		μ	**0.58	**0.46	**0.47	0.17	**0.49
		$A-B$	**-0.44	0.44	-0.17	**0.91	0.19
		$A+B$	-0.11	**0.78	**0.63	**0.49	**0.76
		$B/(A+B)$	**0.31	-0.20	*0.22	**-0.58	-0.02
	2AFC	A	0.02	**0.58	0.09	**0.77	**0.35
		B	0.16	**0.53	**0.91	**-0.68	**0.76
		μ	**0.53	0.02	-0.36	**0.63	-0.18
		$A-B$	-0.07	0.15	*-0.42	**0.95	-0.15
		$A+B$	0.12	**0.85	**0.66	0.25	**0.79
		$B/(A+B)$	0.29	-0.08	*0.44	**-0.87	0.20
Experiment 2	low-YN	A	** -0.65	**0.73	0.27	**0.64	**0.60
		B	-0.03	0.23	**0.64	**-0.29	*0.45
		μ	*0.23	*0.29	0.32	0.07	*0.34
		$A-B$	**-0.72	**0.66	-0.17	**0.95	*0.34
		$A+B$	**-0.46	**0.61	**0.48	*0.31	**0.62
		$B/(A+B)$	**-0.60	**0.47	0.11	**-0.66	-0.25
	high-YN	A	** -0.63	**0.70	*0.27	**0.66	**0.55
		B	-0.04	*0.24	**0.68	**-0.44	**0.47
		μ	**0.57	0.15	0.15	0.04	0.16
		$A-B$	**-0.56	**0.47	-0.26	**0.95	0.15
		$A+B$	**-0.45	**0.61	**0.56	0.20	**0.63
		$B/(A+B)$	**0.44	*-0.27	0.35	**-0.77	0.01
	2AFC	A	0.04	**0.92	**0.67	**0.44	**0.82
		B	0.16	**0.67	**0.91	**-0.61	**0.82
		μ	**0.37	*0.33	-0.21	*0.96	0.27
		$A-B$	-0.12	0.24	-0.21	**0.96	0.01
		$A+B$	0.12	**0.95	**0.95	-0.10	**0.96
		$B/(A+B)$	0.11	*-0.24	0.01	**-0.53	-0.11

Table 6: Correlations of model parameters $\{A, B, \mu, A-B, A+B, B/(A+B)\}$ with the measured variables $\{P_A, T_A, T_B, \Delta T, T_M\}$. Significant correlations, with Spearman's method, are indicated at 0.05 (*) and 0.01 (**) levels. Bold font values are significant correlations that systematically appear across experiments and tasks; grey shaded values are the ones plotted on Figure 10.

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First, the data $\{\gamma, T_A, T_B, \Delta T\}$ corresponding to zero contrast are now analysed as a function of task. Figure 10 depicts all two way correlations between the tasks for each variable. The guess rate of the observers were only correlated between the two YN tasks (as seen in Figs.3,5) but not between 2AFC and YN tasks (Fig.10A-C). Response times for alternative “A” (Fig.10D-F) and “B” (Fig.10G-I) were systematically correlated between all tasks, mainly indicating that observers kept global RTs strategies across measures. On the other hand, differences in RTs between the two alternatives (Fig.10J-L) were only correlated between YN tasks but not between YN and 2AFC tasks. Because this last correlation might be affected by random assignment of response alternatives “A” and “B” in the 2AFC task when compared to the YN tasks, the correlation was repeated by re-assigning T_A 's the “Interval 1” RTs with $\gamma > 0.5$ and “Interval 2” RTs with $\gamma < 0.5$, and for T_B 's the other ones. The results also gave non significant effects (Exp.1: low-YN vs. 2AFC – $r=0.30$, $p=0.30$, high-YN vs. 2AFC – $r=-0.04$, $p=0.87$; Exp.2: low-YN vs. 2AFC – $r=-0.14$, $p=0.18$, high-YN vs. 2AFC – $r=-0.13$, $p=0.20$). The overall analysis shows that observers rather tend to keep very similar RTs strategies between the three independent measures, but that RTs differences between the two alternatives are similar only within YN tasks.

These results combined with the insights gained in the previous section (Fig.9) hint to the fact that DDM's prediction of low- and high-YN tasks should give similar proportion responses “Yes” as a function of contrast in both measures.